

AN APPROACH TO UNDERSTANDING MAN FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF DUALISM AND MONISM

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Abstract: The approach to human understanding through the perspectives of dualism and monism is one of the important topics of philosophy. These approaches influence how we understand the human self and the relationship between mind and body.

Key words: dualism, philosophy, monism, consciousness.

Enter. The place and importance of the concept of man in philosophy - this topic has been the focus of attention of thinkers and philosophers throughout history. In the field of philosophy, man is the main object of study to understand the complexity and uniqueness of mind, body and spirituality.

Plato's Concept of Humanity:

For example, ancient philosophers like Plato studied the mental abilities and the spiritual part of man. He explained the human soul in relation to the world of ideal essence and ideas. This helped a person to understand the world of knowledge and qualities more deeply.

The Importance of Man in Philosophy:

The concept of man in philosophy, in turn, is a basic concept for various philosophical fields such as ethics, metaphysics, epistemology and anthropology. Understanding the human being and his relationship with the environment, as well as analyzing our ways of knowing and mental capacities, is one of the most basic questions in philosophy.

Main Areas of Study:

Another important direction of philosophical studies is the analysis of human interaction with other people and society. It refers to the complexity of relationships and social interactions, while also being associated with moral, political and cultural norms and values.

Human Self-Concept:

Philosophy also studies the ways of self-expression and personal identity of a person. This language contains a comprehensive view of human understanding through approaches to self-understanding, personal experience, and the study of consciousness.

The main tenets of dualism cover complex ideas in philosophy, especially regarding the separation of mind and body or brain and soul. This concept is primarily a component of René Descartes and his ideas based on the saying "Cogito, ergo sum" ("I think, therefore I am"). Dualism claims that every being consists of two main parts: consciousness (mental) and physical (physical).

The Basic Principles of Dualism include:

1. Substantial Dualism: This is a principle advanced by Descartes, which states that mind (soul) and body are two independent entities. These two substances can interact with each other, but the existence of each is independent of the other.

2. Propertial Dualism (Property Dualism): This applies the idea that mind and body are related substances, but their properties are sharply differentiated.

3. Dual Structure Theory: Dualism states that the structure and functioning of the mind is fundamentally different from that of the physical world. Consciousness does not work without abstract concepts, without knowledge of properties, but with its own internal methods.

4. Interdependence and Coherence: Another principle of this is that the human mind and body are interdependent systems that work in harmony with each other.

5. Interaction Theory: Dualistic theories of consciousness talk about the interaction of mind and body; for example, issues such as how our minds can control our bodies or how physical experiences can affect our mental states.

These principles contribute to a deeper analysis of human complexity in dualistic thinking and allow the human experience to be viewed in the context of mind-body interaction.

The main tenets of monism are based on the belief that all existence is united in a single basis. It expresses the idea that there is one principle, one basis, or one substance, and that the whole universe is made up of that one basis.

Basic Principles of Monism:

1. **Existential Monism (Ontological Monism):** This claims that there is only one kind of being in the universe. This takes the form of materialism (all matter) or idealism (all intelligence).
2. **Priority Monism:** All things represent parts of a single being. Here it is asserted that there is a single higher system of existence, and all other things are regarded as parts of this basic system.
3. **Thought Monism (Tokchilik Monism):** This theory emphasizes the existence of only thoughts or perceptions and believes that all events that occur in the world are the result of our consciousness.
4. **Matter Monism:** In this approach, only matter is equated with reality and all phenomena of the universe are essentially explained on the basis of material laws.
5. **Functional Monism:** In this approach, the soul and consciousness are understood as natural functions of the brain, and accordingly, consciousness is seen as part of the natural world.

Through the basic principles of monism, all things can be understood in a single system and the phases of the universe can be integrated into this system. These approaches are important in various philosophical schools and interdisciplinary studies.

Dualism and monism offer important philosophical perspectives in understanding the complexity of humanity. Both of these approaches help analyze the nature of human identity and human experience because they conceptualize the relationship between human consciousness and physicality differently.

Role of Dualism: Dualism, by distinguishing between the mental (conscious) and physical (material) aspects of the human being, considers human psychology and bodily functioning as two separate components. The dualistic approach recognizes the psychological and physical aspects of human experiences and analyzes the

specific characteristics and interaction processes of each separately. For example, mental processes such as emotion and cognition are explained independently of physical brain activity.

The Role of Monism:

Monism, on the other hand, believes that all of existence is unified in a single framework, and views the human mind and body as parts of that single system. Materialistic monism, for example, proposes a complete connection of the processes of consciousness with the biological activity of the brain, which allows a complete understanding of human identity through the brain system.

Human Complexity and Two Approaches:

Dualism and monism illuminate the full spectrum of human complexity in order to understand man, through mental states, cognition, conscious experiences, physical sensations, and other human processes. Both approaches provide important conceptual frameworks for explaining human behavior, decision-making, and cultural, social, and psychological interactions.

Conclusion: Thus, the place and importance of the human concept in philosophy has a great influence on how we perceive the space, society and ourselves that surround us, our decision-making processes and our spiritual quests. These discussions have evolved over the centuries through various schools of thought and are still hotly debated among thinkers and philosophers.

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